

2023

RADx-UP Rapid Research Pilot Program Evaluation

2023 End of Year Evaluation Report
RADx-UP Tracking & Evaluation Team

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Abbreviations

CCPH	Campus Community Partners for Health
CDCC	Coordination and Data Collection Center
CHER	UNC Center for Health Equity Research
C2G	Community Collaboration Grant
DA	Data Analytics
DEI	Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion
EO	Evaluation Objective
EQ	Evaluation Question
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
MSC	Most Significant Change
NIH	National Institutes of Health
PI	Principal Investigator
RADx-UP	Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations
RP2	Rapid Research Pilot Program
SEBI	Social, Ethical, and Behavioral Implications
SECDP	Stakeholder Engagement, Communication, and Dissemination Plan
SEP	Strategic Evaluation Plan
T&E	Tracking & Evaluation
UNC	The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
US	United States

Executive Summary

The 2023 Annual RP2 Evaluation Report details the Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics in Underserved Community (RADx-UP) Rapid Research Pilot Program's (RP2) key evaluation findings. This report explicitly covers the evaluation of **the RADx-UP Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2)** projects from January 1st, 2022 through January 5th 2024.

The Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill (UNC) evaluates RP2. The purpose of this evaluation report is two-fold: 1) describe key evaluation findings that indicate **RADx-UP RP2 program** outputs, outcomes, productivity, and impacts; and 2) Describe the stakeholder-engaged evaluation process of establishing evaluation feedback loops for identifying and addressing areas of improvement. The RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) supports RADx-UP projects as they serve their communities. The CDCC serves as the technical support system and infrastructure to maximize the impact and effectiveness of all projects within the RADx-UP program. The Duke Clinical Research Institute (DCRI) and the Center for Health Equity Research (CHER) at the University of North Carolina (UNC), Chapel Hill, oversee the CDCC.

The T&E team's evaluation results presented in this report are used by the RP2 team to address any issues with awardees in ad hoc meetings and to improve CDCC support and overall understanding of each project's progress towards reaching their intended goals.

Key Findings from Evaluation

- As of March 15th, 2023, the **CDCC has funded 25 RP2 projects across seven funding cycles.**
- This report presents data from project cycles 1-2 and 4-7. There were no funded projects for cycle 3, and cycle 7 is in the process of data collection.
- The most common underserved populations targeted by the RP2 projects include **socioeconomically disadvantaged people, Black and Hispanic/Latino populations, and people living in rural areas.**
- **Currently** funded RP2 projects have enrolled **4,086 participants of the 11,810 participants (34.6%) targeted to be enrolled over the course of the project period.** A **total of 4,948 COVID-19 tests were administered of the 19,709 tests targeted to be administered (25.1%) over the course of the project period.** One project reported a testing target of 9,000. The most common challenges reported during this reporting period by projects (n=13) include **enrollment challenges and testing reporting challenges.**

I. Background

The Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2) is part of the larger, Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Program, which aims to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality. The RADx-UP program seeks to achieve this primary aim by:

- Understanding and alleviating barriers to testing across the nation.
- Utilizing implementation strategies, community-based interventions, and multi-level partnerships to increase the reach, access, acceptance, uptake, and sustainment of US Food and Drug Administration (FDA)-authorized/approved diagnostics among vulnerable populations in geographic locations that are underserved.
- Strengthening the available data on population disparities in infection rates, disease progression, and outcomes; differences in testing access and uptake patterns; and identifying strategies to address inequities in COVID-19 diagnostics.

RP2 awards up to \$200,000 in direct costs for a 12-month period to continuously and responsively assess the feasibility of utilizing implementation strategies, community-based interventions, and multi-level partnerships to increase the reach, access, acceptance, uptake, and sustainment of FDA-authorized/approved COVID-19 diagnostics among vulnerable populations in underserved geographic locations¹. Institutions of higher education, industry, state and local governments, and community-based organizations with the infrastructure to manage such funding are eligible to apply for the RP2 funding¹. RP2 projects are human subject research studies requiring approval from an Institutional Review Board (IRB).

Overview of the RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation

The Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill (UNC), comprehensively assesses the outcomes and impacts of all projects funded within through the RP2 awards. The T&E team frames its evaluation by utilizing core components of the **Translational Science Benefits (TSBM) Model**², the **Reach Effectiveness Adoption Implementation Maintenance (RE-AIM) Framework**^{3,4} and the **Most Significant Change approach**⁵.

- **The Translational Science Benefits (TSBM) Model**² is used to assess the RP2's translation of innovation related to COVID-19 testing into clinical applications, healthcare guidelines, community interventions, policies, and other outcomes that benefit underserved communities at large.
- The team uses the **Reach Effectiveness Adoption Implementation Maintenance (RE-AIM) Framework** to address individual-level and organization-level outcomes and impacts significant to measuring the sustainability and effectiveness of programs^{3,4}.

The RE-AIM components are used to evaluate the wide reach, sustainable adoption, implementation processes, and long-term effects of the RP2 program.

- The team also employs the **Most Significant Change (MSC) approach** to better understand program impact, and the values held by different stakeholders⁵.

An overview of the RADx-UP RP2 aims, outcomes, and associated evaluation key measures are available in **Table 1**. The T&E team also monitors and evaluates how the CDCC program activities improve the RADx-UP program’s effectiveness, performance, and community engagement.

Table 1. Overview of RADx-UP RP2 Aims, Outcomes, and Associated Evaluation Key Measures

Overview of Outcomes and Key Measures		
Outcomes	Measures	Survey Tools Used
Aim 1: Improve access to and uptake of diagnostic COVID-19 testing in underserved, COVID-19 medically, geographically, and socially vulnerable populations.		
Increase individuals reached with testing services or information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of individuals reached through projects (enrolled) • Number of individuals tested • Number of positive tests • Frequency of testing per participant • Number of participants showing one or more symptoms • Underserved populations and COVID-19 vulnerable populations engaged through projects (per cycle and cumulatively) • Diversity of populations reached (geographically, across underserved and vulnerable population categories) 	Bimonthly evaluation surveys via REDCap
Aim 2: Evaluate the feasibility of implementing emerging COVID-19 testing technologies in underserved communities.		
Participants enrolled in each study Expanded RADx-UP Resource Library	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity of organizations funded (location, organization type) • # of new materials/resources added to Resource Library • Number and type of research products resulting from pilot project (publication, new external grant, etc.) 	Program Records Bimonthly evaluation surveys via REDCap
Aim 3: Implement the RP2 program to maximize the impact, effectiveness, and efficiency of RADx-UP CDCC to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality.		

Recruitment of a sufficient number of applicants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of applicants per cycle • # of projects awarded per cycle • # of days between award notification and project initiation 	Program Records
Timely launch of projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilization of RADx-UP resources and support 	Bimonthly evaluation surveys via REDCap
Timely completion of projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of awardees that expended funding in a 12-month grant period • Types of CDCC support used 	
Feedback on utility and quality support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suggested improvements to CDCC support/resources 	

II. Methods

Data Sources. The RADx-UP RP2 evaluation consists of a longitudinal evaluation design, which involves collecting data from RP2 program awardees at seven time points. Data collected includes project updates, activities, outcomes, and use of CDCC support and resources (see [Appendix 1 for the RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation Logic Model](#)). Data sources include RP2 program records, project intake surveys, bimonthly evaluation surveys, and a post-program follow-up survey administered six months after the project closeout date. See [Figure 1](#) for a flow diagram of how the data sources map onto program evaluation.

RP2 Program Records

The RP2 grant administration leadership team works with the T&E team to provide grant administration data such as the number of applicants per cycle.

Project Intake Survey

The T&E team retrieves demographic data on the project target population(s) and project characteristics from the Project Intake Survey completed by the project team at enrollment.

Bimonthly Evaluation Surveys

The T&E team administers bimonthly progress report surveys through REDCap to RP2 awardees based on project start dates. Bimonthly evaluation surveys collect information on project testing and enrollment; challenges faced in completing the program; protocol changes; and tracking self-assessment on meeting milestones. Items on these surveys also assess components of the RE-AIM framework.

The midpoint surveys (6-month) and closeout surveys (12-month or whenever project ends, if extended) contain additional questions to gather data on project outcomes, research productivity, and dissemination of findings; utilization of RADx-UP CDCC support; and

community partner engagement. Items on these evaluation surveys also assess outcomes and impacts with respect to the TSBM Framework indicators.

Follow-up Survey

The T&E team administers a follow-up survey at six months after project completion via REDCap to assess the long-term impacts of the pilot projects. This evaluation includes any sustained project activities and other achievements from the pilot project (such as additional external funding, new partnerships, new publications, etc.). Items on this evaluation survey also assess outcomes and impacts with respect to the MSC approach.

Figure 1. Evaluation Data Sources

Data Analysis. The T&E team analyzes data and shares the findings with the RP2 leadership via dashboard and evaluation reports.

Individual Dashboards

The T&E team summarizes the data findings from the bimonthly evaluation surveys (per awardee) into individualized data summaries/dashboards and shares them with the RP2 team before the subsequent data collection time point. The T&E team codes open-ended response items as categorical variables. Qualitative data include questions about project challenges, roadblocks, and improvements to RADx-UP CDCC support or resources.

Quarterly Aggregate Dashboards

The T&E team aggregates bimonthly evaluation survey data across projects (included data are from projects' most recent completed survey) into quarterly dashboards that contain information about:

- Communities served
- Partner organization types
- Project enrollment and testing numbers
- Challenges reported
- Research products developed
- CDCC Impact and satisfaction

Biannual T&E Evaluation Reports

The T&E team analyzes data from all bimonthly evaluation surveys across projects and presents the findings in biannual evaluation reports (e.g. 6-month and 12-month program reports).

Project Impact Profiles. The T&E team utilizes 6 and 12-month closeout survey data to assess project outcomes according to the Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM) indicators, as shown in the **Figure 2** below ⁶.

The TSBM is a framework designed to support the assessment of clinical and translational research outcomes to measure clinical and community health impacts² (see **Figure 2**). The T&E team uses the core components of TSBM to evaluate the impact of the RP2 program's potential clinical, community, economic, and policy benefits related to increased access to COVID-19 testing, vaccination, and community-led engagement initiatives in underserved communities. The T&E team includes an additional impact indicator — health equity — to describe the impact profiles of projects that focus on dismantling inequities and addressing the social determinants of health in testing among underserved populations.

Figure 2. Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM)^{2, 6} + Health Equity Impact Areas

 CLINICAL	Clinical and Medical Benefits (procedures, guidelines, tools, and products)
 COMMUNITY	Community and Public Health Benefits (health activities, care, and promotion)
 ECONOMIC	Economic Benefits (commercial products, financial savings, and benefits)

<p data-bbox="224 453 399 478">HEALTH EQUITY</p>	<p data-bbox="716 338 1154 407">Health Equity Benefits* (accessibility, adaptability, reach)</p>
<p data-bbox="269 680 349 705">POLICY</p>	<p data-bbox="651 575 1224 644">Policy and Legislative Benefits (advisory activities, policies, and legislation)</p>

*The TSBM Framework has been adapted for this evaluation to include an indicator for Health Equity benefits.

Most Significant Change. The Most Significant Change (MSC) technique is an evaluation method that involves collecting significant change stories from the field, and having a panel of designated stakeholders select the most significant of these stories³. MSC informs program impact and unintended changes, how and when a change came to be, and also helps provide an understanding on the values of different stakeholders. We use an adapted MSC approach in the evaluation. In the post project follow up survey, an open text question asks respondents to share what they felt was the most significant change that resulted from their project.

III. Results

The following section details the process and outcome evaluation results from the bimonthly evaluation surveys collected between January 1 through December 31, 2023, and analyzed and summarized across projects.

A. Process Evaluation Results

RP2 Program Grant Application Process and Award Utilization

Currently, there are **25 RP2 projects across funding cycles** (Cycle 1 n=8 funded projects; Cycle 2 n=1 funded project; there were no funded projects in Cycle 3, Cycle 4 n=4 funded projects, Cycle 5 n=3 projects, Cycle 6 n=3 projects, and Cycle 7 n=6). **Table 2** below shows the metrics per RP2 funding cycle for the application process and notification of awards.

Table 2. Metrics per RP2 Funding Cycle for the Grant Application Process, Notification of Award, and Funding Expenditure by Awardees

RP2 Project Cycle	Application Period	Number of Applicants Received per cycle	Number of Projects Awarded per cycle	Award Rate	Average number of days between award notification and Project initiation

Cycle 1	3/3/21 – 4/16/21	9	8	88.8%	182
Cycle 2	5/7/21 - /6/18/21	5	1	20%	79
Cycle 3	7/2/21 - 8/13/21	0	0	-	-
Cycle 4	10/29/21 - 12/10/21	8	4	50%	60 [^]
Cycle 5	4/1/22 – 5/13/22	3	3	100%	72
Cycle 6	8/5/22 - 9/16/22	7	3	43%	NA
Cycle 7	12/2/2022- 1/13/2023	11	6	55%	106

[^]The number reflects the average of three of the four awarded projects in the cycle. The fourth project was excluded because the average number of days between award notification and project initiation (160 days) was significantly longer than the other three projects.

Satisfaction with CDCC Administration Resources and Support. Figure 3 summarizes the results from the 6-month or 12-month evaluation surveys, whichever is the most recent survey regarding project satisfaction with the application and award process. Overall, projects reported satisfaction with RADx-UP CDCC administration's support regarding the application process. **Over 85% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with each statement** that asked about receiving adequate support completing their application and having a Request For Application (RFA) that was easy to understand to projects.

Fig 3: RP2 Project Satisfaction with CDCC Administration Resources and Support (n=21 projects reporting)

*Not Applicable responses were not included in the visual.

Satisfaction with the support provided by the RP2 administration team. Figure 4 summarizes the results from the 6-month or 12-month evaluation surveys-which-ever is the most recent survey-regarding project satisfaction with the support provided by the RP2 administration team. Overall, projects reported satisfaction with the RP2 administration team. **About 90% of respondents reported that they are very satisfied or satisfied with the knowledge in resolving project and the response time to request.**

Fig 4: RP2 Project Satisfaction with RP2 Administration (*n=21 projects reporting*)

Outcome Evaluation Results

B1. Sociodemographic Results

Characteristics of RP2 Projects

Geographic Diversity. RP2-funded projects (*n= 25*) are spread out throughout the US, with the majority located in the South, Southwest, and West regions. **Figure 5** below shows the geographic diversity of RP2 Projects across the United States (US). The top six states with the highest number of cumulative cases (per 100,000) are Rhode Island, Alaska, Kentucky, North Dakota, and Tennessee⁷.

Underserved Populations Served. Figure 7 provides a breakdown of underserved populations served by RP2 projects. Underserved populations are *populations that the NIH has identified as being underrepresented in biomedical research and known to experience greater morbidity and mortality because of socioeconomic factors*⁹. This data shows that RP2 projects have a broad reach of underserved populations. During this reporting period, the most common underserved population served by RP2 projects is socioeconomically disadvantaged populations.

Fig 7: Underserved Populations Served by Projects (n=25 projects reporting)

*One project can have more than one minority serving institution

COVID-19 Vulnerable Communities Served. Figure 8 displays the vulnerable communities served by RP2 projects. COVID-19 vulnerable communities are *populations that the NIH has identified as being at greater risk of COVID-19 infection and poor health outcomes from COVID-19*¹⁰. When taken together, RP2 projects have a wide reach of COVID-19 vulnerable communities. Of the projects reported during this period, people with comorbidities and immigrants were the most common COVID-19 vulnerable communities served by RP2 projects.

Figure 8: Vulnerable Communities Served by Projects (n=25 projects reporting)

*One project can serve more than one COVID-19 vulnerable community.

Characteristics of RP2 Projects' Partners. Figure 9 highlights projects' community partner organizations. One project reported 25 partner organizations. In earlier reporting cycles, **most projects identified community organizations or non-profit organizations as partners**, but in Cycle 4 we see more local government partners, which could include public health departments or social service agencies.

Figure 9: Characteristics of RP2 Projects' Partners (n= 19 projects reporting)

*6 projects did not report having any partner organizations.

*One project can have more than one partner organization

B2. RP2 Project Testing and Enrollment Outcomes

RP2 Projects Testing and Enrollment. One of the main aims of the RP2 program is to improve access to and uptake of diagnostic COVID-19 testing in underserved, medically, geographically, and socially vulnerable populations. **Figure 10** shows the percentage of the targeted enrollment across all cycles. Enrollment numbers are collected from projects' most recent timepoint. This data informs the program outcome of increasing numbers of individuals reached with testing services or information. Of the 20 projects that reported enrollment numbers, **there have been a total of 4,086 participants enrolled out of the 11,810 participants (34.6%) targeted for enrollment by the end of their project period.**

Figure 10: Percentage of the Targeted Enrollment across all Cycles (*n=20 project reporting*)

**five projects have not yet report enrollment numbers.*

Figure 11 show the percentage of testing target reached across all cycles with **a total of 4,948 tests administered out of the 19,709 total tests (25.1%) they are targeting to administer by the end of their project period across all cycles.** One project reported 9,000 as the targeted testing number.

Figure 11: Percentage of Testing Target Reached by Cycle (*n= 20 projects reporting*)

**5 projects have not yet reported testing numbers.*

Challenges Experienced by Projects. The T&E team also asked projects to report on any roadblocks or challenges faced completing their project in open-ended survey questions. The bimonthly evaluation surveys capture challenges related to sample collection, testing, test result reporting, and community- engagement. The T&E team reviewed these challenges and coded the responses into several categories.

Of the 13 projects that reported on challenges experienced, **the most common were related to enrollment and testing reporting challenges and there were no challenges related to pandemic related delays.** *Enrollment challenges* are defined as challenges/delays in recruiting subjects for research once a testing site has been established. *Testing reporting challenges* are defined as challenges in obtaining results from tests or reporting test results to patients. **Table 3** lists the codes that the T&E team developed for responses to questions that ask projects to *describe any challenges to sample collection, testing, test result reporting, engaging with community members, and any other challenges not mentioned.*

As challenges are observed, the T&E team communicates these challenges to leadership so they can be addressed promptly. Testing reporting, partnerships, and enrollment challenges may be opportunities for learning when strategizing for future large-scale testing projects.

Table 3. Challenges Experienced by Projects

Code	Quotes
Administrative	<i>"Budget is limited as we have to allocate enough budget for testing and compensation of subjects, and so we have limited staffing on the study who help in reporting results."</i>
Enrollment	<i>"While it has not been realized as a confirmed challenge, some community partners who participated in our April program kickoff event expressed concerns that their constituents may not be interested in COVID-19 testing, even if it is free. They cited COVID 'fatigue' when it came to messaging and confusion among the community about if there is still a 'need' for testing."</i>
Testing Administration	<i>"Packet inserts and vending machine exterior did not have any instructions in Spanish. UI video on loop is not clear that captioning will be in Spanish."</i>
Regulatory	<i>"Delays with IRB approvals for our study implementation phase."</i>
Partnerships	<i>"Community partners are exhausted at that time since many of them have participated in many clinical studies at the beginning of pandemic till now. They are also asking for high financial compensation for their time and effort, which we cannot afford due to limited budget. Challenges in finding community partners."</i>
Testing Procurement	<i>"The NIH testing core restricted use of FDA approved tests as described in the intended use of the package insert. Since many of our subjects have no symptoms, we have to use RT-PCR, which is very expensive test compared to the antigen test."</i>
Testing Reporting	<i>"We had difficulties with people not reading instructions or checklists when dropping off samples. People did not add their names and DOB appropriately. There were a few people who did not check their samples in on our LIMS system appropriately. Most of the time we were able to call the patients and fix these mistakes; Only when patient did not include DOB and Name as 2 patient identifiers. We were unable to report because these samples had to be rejected by the lab."</i>

B3. RP2 Project Outcomes and Impacts

RP2 Project Outcomes Aligned with the Translational Sciences Benefit Model (TSBM)

Indicators. In this section, we summarize the results from RP2 projects who completed midpoint and/or closeout surveys as of December 31, 2023. Projects are asked to list their project's main outcomes and for each outcome listed, they are asked to indicate the impact area of the Translational Sciences Benefit Model with which it best aligns. This information is used to evaluate the impact of the RP2 program in demonstrating the clinical, community, economic, and policy benefits of investing in increased access to COVID-19 testing, vaccination, and community-led engagement initiatives in underserved communities.

Currently when asked to report on project outcomes and with what TSBM key benefit area these outcomes fall within, **the majority fall within the Community and Public Health impact area, followed by the Clinical impact area** (see **Figure 12**). Many reported outcomes are related to promoting and increasing COVID-19 testing uptake and accessibility among different target communities. This was done, for example, through assessments to understand the barriers and facilitators to COVID-19 testing uptake, implementation of culturally-tailored telehealth education sessions delivered by community health workers, and identifying benefits and challenges of shelter-based rapid testing on shelter operations. Some clinical outcomes reported include embedding high sensitivity testing within a homeless shelter, incorporating digital reporting systems of health-related tests and providing a new tool to diagnose SARS-Cov2 in clinical settings. It should be noted that these outcomes are potential benefits, rather than achieved benefits, as most projects lasted for a short period of time and actual impacts might not have been evaluated.

Figure 12: RP2 Project Outcomes Aligned with the TSM Indicators (*n= 21 projects reporting*)

**One project can report more than one Translational Science Benefit.*

Projects' Research Products. The T&E team tracks RP2 and other RADx-UP peer-reviewed publications and other scholarly products to understand how projects are developing and disseminating information. **Figure 13** breaks down the types of research products that projects have developed. Almost all projects report they **have developed at least one research product**.

Figure 13: RP2 Research Products (n= 19 projects reporting)

*One project can report more than one research product.

IV. Key Takeaways and Conclusion

RP2 projects advanced COVID-19 testing research by improving access to and uptake of COVID-19 testing in communities of underserved and vulnerable populations across the United States. There were 25 geographically diverse RP2 projects across 7 funding cycles that majorly served socioeconomically disadvantaged populations. Most common vulnerable populations included people with comorbidities and immigrants.

By funding innovative and diverse rapid pilot grants, the RADx-UP consortium was able to identify and address the barriers and facilitators to effective testing and implementing testing programs within underserved communities. Through effective grant administration and research support, the CDCC helped the awardees achieve their implementation (testing, participant enrollment, community engagement) goals.

Most projects reported partnerships with community-based organizations/ non-profit organizations suggesting that these organizations may be pivotal in project awareness and implementation especially in short term projects. RP2 projects collaborated with community-based organizations and diverse stakeholders to reduce barriers to testing, guide testing implementation strategies and built trusted relationships with community partners. Research partnerships developed through the awards can help researchers, the NIH and the CDCC develop sustainable research infrastructure that can be used within future research consortiums as well as increase community capacity for research.

However, RP2 projects identified challenges especially related to motivating participants to enroll in testing programs and report test results back to their projects after self-testing (test reporting). Administrative delays as a result of shifting testing guidelines and limited time capacity because of short funding period/rapid funding cycles (one year) could have worsened some of the enrollment and testing challenges experienced by projects. To ameliorate these

burdens in future pilot programs, the NIH and coordination center can extend grant funding period of rapid pilot programs to 18 months or 2 years so as to account for project administrative delays in start-up phases.

Results indicates that COVID-19 fatigue influenced the capacity of projects to meet enrollment and testing targets. Survey results indicated that participant enrollment was higher during earlier funded cycles compared to later cycles, possibly due to COVID-19 fatigue. Therefore, future multi-cohort pilot programs focused on pandemic-related health outcomes may consider having differing target goals for projects depending on their project cycles. Current RP2 projects should also consider adjusting their targets to account for pandemic-related challenges.

Next Steps. In the remainder of the RP2 program, the T&E team will continue to:

1. Monitor program progress through bimonthly evaluation surveys and reports will be completed every six months.
2. Distribute an 18-month (six months post-project) survey to assess the longer-term impacts of the pilot projects, including any sustained project activities and other achievements that stemmed from the pilot project (additional external funding, new partnerships, etc.) and
3. Support the development of a summative evaluation report, following the end of the pilot programs.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation Logic Model

Rapid Research Pilots Evaluation Logic Model

